

NUMERICAL MODELLING OF COLD-FORMED STEEL Σ -SHAPED BEAMS UNDER FIRE CONDITION

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Summary. *This paper presents the development of a finite element model suitable for predicting the flexural behaviour of cold-formed galvanized steel beams under fire conditions, with different restraining conditions, including no restraint, partial axial restraint to the thermal elongation of the beam and partial rotational restraint at the beam supports. The numerical simulations were performed with the advanced finite element program Abaqus/CAE and the numerical model was compared with some experimental results, in order to validate the developed finite element model and consequently obtain reliable numerical results. This paper provides details of the simulation methodology for achieving numerical stability and faithful representation of detailed structural behaviour. To verify the accuracy of the Abaqus model the numerical and experimental results were compared in terms of axial restraining forces, vertical mid-span deflections, critical temperatures and failure modes of these beams.*

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of cold-formed steel (CFS) members has increased significantly in the past few years due to the large number of advantages that this type of profiles presents when compared to others constructive solutions. The great variety of profiles available allows the building of different member cross-sections and their high strength to weight ratio provides an easier production, assembly and transportation making this material even more popular in construction. Nevertheless, as cold-formed steel members have high slenderness (width-to-thickness ratio) and low torsional stiffness, those members are very susceptible to instability phenomena and can fail in a variety of buckling modes including local, distortional, global buckling and their interactions¹, resulting in complex methods to calculate the strength of CFS

members. These buckling modes are mainly responsible for the ultimate strength of the compression members, once they may precede the cross-section yield.

So far, in spite of the growing popularity of these steel structures, the research on cold-formed steel structural elements under fire conditions is still scarce. Consequently, specific standards for fire design of CFS structures were have not been established yet, resulting in inadequate fire design guidelines for this type of members²⁻⁵. Therefore, it is extremely important to investigate and assess the structural performance of CFS flexural members under fire conditions.

In this context, the numerical modelling becomes hugely important, since a numerical model fulfil adequately the features of interest concerning the behaviour of cold-formed steel members at elevated temperatures⁶⁻⁷, and it is possible to prove that the calibrated model can be used to accurately conduct future numerical parametric studies to provide valuable data to help developing detailed understanding of flexural behaviour of CFS beams subjected to fire.

In this sense, the purpose of this paper is describing the development of a finite element model suitable for predicting the flexural behaviour of CFS Σ -shaped beams under fire conditions, as well as investigate the influence of the axial and rotational restraining on the fire behaviour of these beams. The numerical simulations were performed with the advanced finite element program Abaqus/CAE⁸ and the numerical model was compared with some experimental results⁹, in order to validate the developed finite element model and consequently obtain reliable numerical results. The assessment of the accuracy of the developed numerical models was conducted by comparing the axial restraining forces, vertical displacements, critical temperatures and failure modes obtained from finite element simulations with the corresponding experimental test.

2 FINITE ELEMENT MODELING

2.1 General

In order to simulate the structural behaviour of cold-formed steel beams under combined flexural loading and fire conditions, numerical models were developed using the finite element package Abaqus⁸ - a powerful computational tool for modelling structures with material and geometric nonlinear behaviour. The models were constructed based on the test set-up of Laím *et al.*⁹ and the calibration was done comparing the numerical results with the experimental results obtained by that authors, in order to validate the developed finite element model and to consequently obtain reliable numerical results. In this section, a brief description of the experimental test set-up and procedure is firstly presented, followed by a detailed description of the modelling approach and its verification against experimental data available.

The study performed by the Laím *et al.*⁹ consist in 18 experimental tests on CFS sigma-shaped beams (Figure 1a), composed of one or two (sigma beam and 2-sigma beam) sigma-shaped profiles with nominal thickness of 2.5 mm and connected by carbon steel self-drilling screws. Six of which were just simply supported beams, 6 others were the same beams but with restrained thermal elongation, and the others were beams with axial and rotational restraint. The experimental campaign carried out, is defined in the Table 1, where $2\Sigma_{ra+rr_1}$ denote the first test (1) of the 2Σ (2-sigma beam) with axial (ra) and rotational (rr) restraint.

The span of the studied beams was 3000 mm and they were supported by a roller and pinned support. Four restraining steel beams were provided at each end of the beam to simulate the axial restraint to the thermal elongation of the beam and the rotational stiffness of their supports, as schematically shown in Figure 1b. These experimental tests were performed in two stages: loading and heating stage. First, the beams were loaded at two points 1000 mm (one-third of the beam span) from the supports of the beam (four-point bending test) until achieve 50 % of the design value of the load-bearing capacity of the beams at ambient temperature (P_0) and calculated in accordance with the methods proposed in Eurocode 3¹⁰⁻¹². Finally, after the desired load was reached, the specimens were heated with an electric furnace, programmed to reproduce as near as possible to the standard fire curve ISO 834¹³. During the heating period, the load was kept constant until the specimen buckled. A detailed information regarding the experimental research can be found in the study of Laím *et al.*⁹.

Next, it is described in detail the parameters, considerations and assumptions took into account in the developed nonlinear finite element model to predict the fire performance of such beams.

Test reference	P_0 (kN)	ra (kN/mm)	rr (kN.m/rad)
Σ_i	11,24	0	0
$2\Sigma_i$	34,15	0	0
Σ_{ra_i}	11,24	15	0
$2\Sigma_{ra_i}$	34,15	15	0
Σ_{ra+rr_i}	11,24	15	150
$2\Sigma_{ra+rr_i}$	34,15	15	150

Table 1: Test Plan ($i = 1, 2$ or 3)

Figure 1: (a) Studied beams cross-sections; (b) Axial and rotational restraining system: 1: tested beam; 2: roller support; 3: pinned support; 4 and 5: axial restraining; 6 and 7 : rotational restraining; 8, 9 and 10- load cell; 11 - concrete slab [10]

2.2 Geometrical modeling

For the purpose of reproducing the behaviour of the tested beams with great accuracy, a three-dimensional numerical model was created trying to replicate as close as possible the experimental test set-up⁹ previously mentioned (Figure 1b). The CFS beams were created by defining the cross-sectional profile using center line dimensions and extruding the cross-section

in the longitudinal direction to the required length. Additionally, four rigid plates were initially generated separately and subsequently were attached to the beams to simulate the four-point bending test. Two of them were used to represent the beam supports and the other two were used to obtain a uniform distribution of the load across the surface of the beam. The 2-sigmas section was connected back-to-back by screws which were created and assembled by translating and rotating them to the required location. The 3D model is shown in Figure 2.

2.3 Loading, contact modelling and boundary conditions

The applied load was simulated with concentrated nodal forces ($-Y$ -direction) acting vertically at the middle of rigid plates connected to the upper flange surface of the beams. The application points of the load were located at a distance of one-third of the beam span ($L/3$).

To simulate the required simply supported boundary conditions, a reference node in the middle of the rigid plate was selected to control the motion of that surface. The reference node used to represent the pinned support was constrained against all degrees of freedom excluding the rotational about X -axis. On the other hand, to simulate the roller support the displacement along horizontal axis (Z -direction) was not restrained too. In addition, to avoid the lateral deformation of the beams, all nodes located at the edges of the supports were restrained against lateral translation (X - direction). Finally, the end sections of the finite element models were coupled to two concentric reference points, where a linear spring model was associated in order to achieve the same axial and rotational restraint conditions utilized in the experimental tests. The value of these axial spring was the same considered in the tests.

Figure 2: FE model developed for 2 sigma beams under fire conditions with axial and rotational restraint

Concerning the built-up sigma cross-section, following the methodology adopted in similar studies on CFS bolted profiles^{7, 14, 15}, the contact interactions between the web surfaces of the profiles (Figure 3b) were defined by using the “surface-to-surface” contact discretization

method with a finite-sliding tracking formulation, which is suitable for models with a large plastic deformation. As contact interaction property it was adopted a tangential friction coefficient of 0.2 for the behaviour in tangential direction, a “hard” contact properties were enforced for the normal direction behaviour to minimize penetration of slave surfaces into master surfaces which might occur if plates bend significantly and the penalty method was defined as the constraint enforcement between the steel profile surfaces. A linear damping coefficient was also adopted. Additionally, to model the contact between the two CFS profiles and the self-drilling screws (Figure 3c) a rough and hard contact was assumed, preventing the sliding between surfaces and allowing the transmission of compressive forces, respectively.

The temperature during the experimental tests were measured at different points of the specimen’s cross-section. So, in order to reproduce the non-uniform temperature distribution observed in the experimental campaign, influence areas were defined depending on the position of specific thermocouple. To simulate the heating of the beams, it was assumed that the temperatures in these areas were uniform and equal to the respective thermocouples and each measured temperature was inputted along that area as a function of time. It is important to mention that the temperature was considered uniform in the longitudinal direction of the beam and that the temperature was considered uniform and equal to 20 °C at beam supports (Figure 3a).

Figure 3: (a) Temperature non-uniform distribution introduced in FE model at 483 seconds of the analysis; and detail of the contact between (b) profiles and (c) self-drilling screws and the CFS profile.

2.4 Elements types and meshing

The cold-formed steel beams were modelled by using the general-purpose element S4R (4-node doubly curved general-purpose shell, reduced integration with hourglass control), which has been extensively and successfully utilized to model thin-walled structural elements under fire conditions^{2,6,7}. This element type takes transverse shear deformation into account as well as the thick shell elements. Regarding the self-drilling screws used in built-up 2-sigma beams, the finite element chosen was the C3D8R (8-node hexahedral element, continuum, linear reduced integration with hourglass control).

Simulations have been conducted with the aim of defining an appropriate and accurate finite element model with a reduced computational time. By performing mesh sensitivity analyses, a mesh size of 10 mm x 30 mm for the flat plate sections was found to be optimal, so that an additional refinement did not provide a remarkable improvement in accuracy. However, to achieve better results, smaller elements were used to model the rounded corner regions (Figure 4(a) e (b)). With regard to the screws, a mesh size of approximately 2 mm was assumed⁷ (Figure 4(c)).

Figure 4: Finite element mesh of the sigma beams (a); 2-sigma beams (b) and the screw (c)

2.5 Material modelling

For elastic analysis the sigma beam was assumed to have linear elastic material with Young's modulus of 210 GPa and Poisson's ratio of 0.3. On the other hand, for non-linear analysis, the material of the beam was modelled with von Mises criteria and strain hardening. The stress-strain curves of CFS material were obtained from the model proposed by Laím *et al*⁵ and based on the real curves taken from tensile coupon tests¹⁴. This model is comprised of a gradual yielding behaviour followed by a considerable period of strain hardening, with a nominal yield strength of 320 MPa, a tensile strength of 390 MPa and a Young's modulus of 210 GPa. For the steel screws it was adopted an elastic-perfectly plastic behaviour⁷. Note that the residual stresses were not considered in this study, as assumed by other researchers^{7,15, 16}.

Figure 5: Mechanical and thermal properties: (a) Mechanical properties with temperature increase; (b) Relative thermal elongation

Since the analysis of post-buckling may involve large inelastic strains, the nominal (engineering) static stress-strain curve was converted to a true stress and logarithmic plastic strain curve. Figure 5a shows the stress-strain curves for different temperatures used as input in the numerical simulations. The thermal elongation (Figure 5b) was taken from the predictions proposed by Chen and Young¹⁷, because the one established in Eurocode was found to be over-conservative^{14,17}. Though, the reduction factors for the modulus of elasticity and yield strength of steel at elevated temperatures were obtained from the annex E of EN 1993-1-2:2004¹⁸.

2.6 Analysis Method

Finite elements (FE) three-dimensional models were created for all tested cross-sections under fire conditions with different restraining conditions, including (i) no restraint; (ii) partial axial restraint to the thermal elongation of the beam; and (iii) partial rotational restraint at the beam supports. It has been conducted two different types of numerical analyses, namely linear

eigenvalue buckling analysis and nonlinear buckling analysis. Firstly, a linear perturbation analysis was performed in order to establish the buckling modes and eigenvalues of an ideal linear elastic beam. Several possible buckling modes were obtained from the perturbation by using eigen-modes prediction. From this step, it was chosen buckling modes shapes to introduce as initial geometric imperfections into the finite element model in the nonlinear analysis. Trying to entirely reproduce the final deformed shape observed in the experimental tests⁹, an interaction between different buckling modes were considered, and the maximum values assumed for the magnitude of imperfections was: $L/500$ for global imperfections, $2t$ for distortional imperfections and $h/100$ for local imperfections.

Upon incorporation of the geometric imperfections into the developed numerical models, nonlinear buckling analysis, accounting for both material and geometric nonlinearities, was carried out to replicate the full range of the fire-resistant tests for all the conditions tested in the experimental analysis. As in the experimental tests, this analysis occurs in two steps: first the serviceability load (P_0) was gradually applied on the beams and then it was conducted the heating phase where the load was kept constant until the structure becomes unstable, where the beam deformation was large enough, $L^2/(400h) = 88$ mm (failure criteria in terms of deformation for flexural elements¹³), which roughly corresponds to the time when the beams lose their capacity to resist against the axial restraining forces (failure criteria in terms of strength), in other words, when the axial restraining force return to their initial value. As a consequence, for this study it was assumed that the critical temperature resisted by the studied beam corresponds exactly to the one measured at that critical time. A “static general” option featuring a full Newton-Raphson solution technique was used for the static nonlinear analysis of the beams due to this method having provision for numerical stabilization which were required during the analysis.

3 VALIDATION OF FINITE ELEMENT MODELS

Assessment of the accuracy of the developed numerical models (Abaqus) was conducted by comparing the displacement-temperature curves of the simply supported beams (Figure 6 (a1,a2)), axial restraining force-temperature curves of the axially and rotationally restrained beams (Figure 6 (b1,b2,c1,c2)), critical temperatures (Table 2) and failure modes (Figure 7) obtained from finite element simulations with the corresponding experimental.

As observed in Figure 6, the result of Abaqus simulation was relatively close to the experimental results, since all developed FEM predicted curves comparable to the experimental ones, especially in which concerns the maximum axial restraining force supported by the beams and the critical temperatures. As specified in Table 2, the mean differences between the critical temperature obtained from the tests and FEA are less than 7 %, indicating that the estimated results were in good agreement with the presented in experimental data. So, it is possible to state that the finite element developed can accurately reproduce the behaviour of flexural CFS beams under fire conditions and with axial and rotational restraint.

On the other hand, Figure 7 presents the experimental deformed configuration of the tested beam (Figure 7 (a1, b1)) and the corresponding deformation pattern predicted by the numerical analysis (Figure 7 (a2, b2) after completing the test and analysis respectively, indicating excellent agreement. Overall, the FE models developed are capable of accurately replicating

the experimental responses of CFS beams under fire conditions, ensuring a strong validity of the developed finite element model. As observed in the experimental tests and validated by the numerical analysis, the lateral-torsional buckling was the main failure mode responsible for the collapse of the beams. Besides the lateral-torsional buckling, failure modes of these beams also involved distortional and local buckling, although the magnitudes of local deformations were observed to be small and less visible, due to the extensive lateral rotation of the beam.

Figure 6: Evolution of the vertical displacement as a function of the mean temperature of the beams (a1, a2) and the evolution of the axial restraining forces as a function of the average temperature of the beams (b1, b2, c1, c2)

4 CONCLUSIONS

By using a finite element analysis, it was intended to reproduce the effect of temperature

increase on the structural behaviour of beam under different restraints conditions, aiming to obtain models capable of reproducing the experimental results. The finite element models developed were presented and validated in terms of the maximum generated axial restraint forces, vertical displacements, critical temperatures and failure modes.

The good agreement between the experimental observations and the numerical simulations confirms that the finite element models developed with the Abaqus solver are suitable for predicting the structural fire behaviour of cold-formed steel beams. Thus, it can be stated that the developed finite element models can be used to accurately conduct future numerical parametric studies, in order to model the fire resistance and behaviour of these beams outside the bounds of the original experimental tests⁹. As a consequence, providing valuable data to help developing detailed understanding of flexural behaviour of CFS beams subjected to fire.

Sigma beams				2 - Sigma beams			
Experimental tests	Critical temperature [°C]		Relative error [%]	Experimental tests	Critical temperature [°C]		Relative error [%]
	Experimental results	ABAQUS			Experimental results	ABAQUS	
Σ_{01}	669	643	-3,95	$2\Sigma_{01}$	594	585	-1,57
Σ_{02}	680		-5,52	$2\Sigma_{02}$	601		-2,61
Σ_{03}	693		-7,22	$2\Sigma_{03}$	632		-7,50
Mean	681	643	-5,58	Mean	609	585	-3,96
$\Sigma_{ra_{01}}$	526	531	1,04	$2\Sigma_{ra_{01}}$	540	506	-6,27
$\Sigma_{ra_{02}}$	607		-12,55	$2\Sigma_{ra_{02}}$	524		-3,53
$\Sigma_{ra_{03}}$	564		-5,83	$2\Sigma_{ra_{03}}$	509		-0,57
Mean	566	531	-6,11	Mean	524	506	-3,51
$\Sigma_{ra+rr_{01}}$	666	681	2,30	$2\Sigma_{ra+rr_{01}}$	574	606	5,47
$\Sigma_{ra+rr_{02}}$	622		9,55	$2\Sigma_{ra+rr_{02}}$	614		-1,30
$\Sigma_{ra+rr_{03}}$	668		1,94	$2\Sigma_{ra+rr_{03}}$	626		-3,23
Mean	652	681	4,48	Mean	605	606	0,18

Table 2: Critical temperature comparison between experimental and Abaqus results

Figure 6: Numerical (a1, b1) and experimental (a2, b2) failure modes for the sigma beam (a1, a2) with axial and rotational restraint and for 2-sigma beam (b1, b2) with axial restraint

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